

ACTIVITIES OF FORMING PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF THE MUSIC CULTURE TEACHER

Narzullayeva Nodira Saydullayevna
Almazor District Specialized State Secondary
School No. 133 Teacher of Music Culture
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12683653>

Abstract: This article examines the processes of forming the pedagogical skills of a teacher of music culture. Also, the requirements for the pedagogue, principles of teaching, organization of lessons, didactic games and demonstration methods for the lesson to increase the interest of students are highlighted. The need to train today's pedagogic personnel, adapt their knowledge to world standards, and provide them with the necessary information for education and training is explained. The goals and tasks of the pedagogue in increasing the effectiveness of the music lesson, as well as the skills and abilities of developing relationships with the student are highlighted.

Key words: pedagogue, music culture, activity, student, lesson processes, professional skill, musical skill, creator. skillful, friendly attitude, national education.

Introduction:

Great attention is paid to today's youth, especially in the field of education, conditions and opportunities are created for them. On the initiative of the head of our state Sh. Mirziyoyev, contract fees for women and girls to receive master's education have been paid by the state since this year. Also, in the youth policy, a lot of attention is paid to young people, because respecting the opinions of young people and giving them support is one of the important issues.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, while reflecting on the current tasks in front of us regarding the reform of the school education system in our country, said, "The greatest building in the world is a school" emphasized his opinion and touched on the essence and importance of this issue [3].

Despite the positive changes implemented, there are still systemic problems in the educational system, the material and technical base of the school, the knowledge and skills of some pedagogical staff do not meet the requirements of today's time. It is necessary to create a modern and rational system in the field of education, to create and update teaching methods, educational standards, textbooks and training manuals, to use best practices abroad in education, and to adhere to national traditions and values in education. the importance of leaning was noted.

The future of the young generation largely depends on the teacher, his potential, professional training, and the work of teaching and educating students. Musical culture lessons are of great importance in the formation of an active person who has matured in all respects, can meet the demands of the present age, embodies spiritual wealth, moral purity, conscience, respect for adults, hard work [3].

The analyzes of the professor of the Cherkassk Institute I.P. Podlasiy, the scientists of the University of Quanta Rua (Mexico) such as M. Sanchez, M. Maribel on the factors that should

be paid attention to during the course of the lesson, and the experience -test works were organized [7].

Today, students studying at the Pedagogical University have great responsibilities, because they need to keep up with the times. Mastering the field of pedagogy, namely the process of forming the pedagogical skills of a teacher of music culture, is one of the urgent problems.

B. Mustafojev's (Music pedagogy. Tashkent; 2022) textbook [1], R. Kadirov's (Music pedagogy, Music publishing house 2018) monograph [5], J. Yuldashev, D. Muratova's (Music Teaching Methodology. Bukhara 2021y) [4] training manual provides information on the occupation of music pedagogues.

It is desirable to be able to correctly choose interactive methods according to the model of education, the direction of the studied science and topic, the scope of the idea, as well as objective, subjective reasons and other aspects [7].

One of the important factors in the formation of pedagogical skills of a teacher of music culture is the creation of the right educational method and its use during lessons.

It is necessary to pay attention to every process in educating future teachers. Today, in modern education, it is important for a teacher not only to acquire professional knowledge, but also to acquire computer technologies, foreign languages, physiology, psychology and other sciences. Discipline is one of the main places in training a good pedagogue. When organizing the organizational aspects of each lesson, it is important for the teacher to pay attention to the rules of etiquette, i.e. not to be late for class, dress code, speech culture, and relations with students during the lesson. It should be noted that professional skills are formed in students in the process of independent work. That is, the pedagogue moves with the times.

Music culture lessons are based on didactic theory and principles of pedagogy. These principles determine the basic requirements of all educational bases - methods of lesson content and the structure of the lesson and its directions - performed by the teacher and the student. The didactic principles of music culture lessons consist of five types:

1. The principle of systematicity, scientificity and attendance in music education and upbringing.
2. The principle of student awareness and activity in the lesson.
3. The principle of demonstration in music culture classes.
4. The principle of matching educational materials to children's knowledge and skills.
5. The principle of consistency of knowledge and skills in music lessons.

These principles are mainly used in the process of using educational materials, creating the content and plan of a music lesson. The general didactic principles noted above are inextricably linked and ensure the consistency of music activities based on the continuity and coherence of the music lesson in accordance with the State Education Standard, taking into account the national characteristics [3].

When choosing musical material, the teacher should determine which ready-made works can be taken and which ones should be given to vanity [2].

In teaching, it is necessary to strive for innovations, to use methods and methods that interest students, to organize didactic games based on computer technologies as much as possible, to use slides, pictures, visual aids of various forms. Mobile applications are especially effective in engaging students and conducting Music Culture lessons. It is important that the

future music culture pedagogy is formed in all aspects. One of the important issues is that they should set themselves a number of tasks, if necessary, and they are:

1. In organizing the lesson, greeting in an unconventional way, that is, with the help of music or poems;
2. When repeating the topic, he repeats the topic through a slide or music and evaluates the students in an unconventional way. (encourages with emoticons or colors)
3. During the lesson, he explains a new topic based on five types of activities, and it is important that he can see the result. (teaches to listen to the song, analyzes, learns)
4. Using games and interactive methods in teaching and strengthening the subject.
5. At the end of the lesson, the homework should be given as simple as possible, in a way that the child can understand.

In performing these tasks, it is important for the Music Culture pedagogy to develop knowledge skills, ability to listen and sing, and performance skills. It is important to create a lesson in the case of developing a system to make each type of activity new and interesting for students. It should also be noted that every minute of the lesson should be spent in a friendly relationship with the students. Systematic and skillful conduct of these processes with a new approach to the structure of the lesson is one of the measures of the pedagogy aimed at a modern approach.

The school team plays an important role in acquiring the professional skills of a teacher, because as a result of discussions and debates in the team, pedagogical skills and attitudes towards the profession are formed, and there is an opportunity to fill unknown skills and qualifications. After every lesson, if there are problematic students, the head of the class will get information about the student's condition, lifestyle, and parents, and only then will he go inside the remaining students and encourage them to study together. At the same time, talking with parents about their children's musical interests, finding solutions to the problems of teaching them national instruments (or any other musical clubs), and attracting them to their clubs is one of the qualities of their pedagogical skills.

Today, music plays an important role in the formation of a person, has an active influence on his emotions and psyche. One of the main tasks of comprehensive schools is to introduce students to the world of sophistication and provide spiritual education. In this, the teacher introduces the child to a specific piece of music, performs it expressively, "lively", attracts the attention of the students, expands the student's speech, thinking ability, worldview, emotional feeling. actively affects them as well.

The content of music lessons includes not only mastering, but also the development of students' minds, their attitude to reality, the formation of their aesthetic culture, and the formation of other inner feelings. The teacher's creative approach to the lesson is important and sets a number of tasks for himself.

Developing new methods and tools in music education; expressing the inextricable connection between life and art. In the implementation of this goal, the teacher should prepare seriously, work tirelessly on himself, that is, to increase the level of knowledge, he should read scientific literature, new programs, fiction literature, go to the theater, museum, and find ways to increase his (students') consciousness. it is necessary to improve [3].

Conclusion:

Thus, in the process of working with the student during the lesson, the pedagogy should encourage the student, create an opportunity for the student to think freely, and have friendly

relations with them. It is important to be able to give individual attention to each student, especially when the music teacher has tools to motivate the students after each question or assignment in the lesson, because the students are aware of the teacher's attention. looks at his attention. It is important that they feel that they are not a teacher of music culture, but an ideal person. Therefore, based on the modern approach to lessons from the music culture pedagogue, the effectiveness of the lesson increases and the skills of music culture pedagogues are formed..

References:

1. B. Mustafoyev. Music pedagogy. Tashkent; 2022.
2. D. Soipova "Music teaching methodology" Tashkent; 2009
3. G. Sharipova, Z. Khadjayeva. "Music teaching methodology" T.; 2020
4. J. Yuldashev, D. Muratova. Music teaching methodology. Bukhara 2021.
5. R. Kadirov's. Music pedagogy., Music Publishing House 2018.
6. Asafiev B.V. Musical form as a process. L.: State. music ed., 1973.